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**An evaluation of the DIADEM real time ocean
forecasting system with the MICOM and EnKF**

by

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abstract

The DIADEM/TOPAZ ocean monitoring and forecasting system is currently up-and-running with support from the European Commission and national research councils. The main objective of the DIADEM project has been to develop an operational ocean and ecosystem monitoring and prediction system for the North Atlantic and Nordic Seas, where focus has been on developing advanced data assimilation techniques for assimilation of remotely sensed data into the ocean and ecosystem models. The assimilation system is operated in real time and provides forecasts of both physical and ecosystem variables. In this paper the DIADEM real time forecasting system will be described in some detail and an attempt to validate the system by using independent temperature and salinity profiles from the Global Temperature and Salinity Pilot Project (GTSP) will be presented.

1 Introduction

The need for high quality forecast of marine parameters is apparent both within offshore and shipping industry, within the navy, commercial fisheries and fish farming. E.g. offshore activities related to drilling and production of oil and gas introduce the need for real time forecasts of oceanic currents which may be important for safety related to critical operations on deep water. Also in future fisheries management systems, information about marine parameters such as nutrients and plankton concentrations and pollutants, will be increasingly important for accurate monitoring and prediction of fishstocks. Thus there are needs for operational monitoring and prediction of both physical and biological marine parameters.

The optimal approach for an operational ocean forecasting system is an integrated use of both high resolution ocean- and ecosystem models and observations of physical, chemical and biological variables. This integration can best be done using data assimilation techniques.

In the EC-project DIADEM (Development of Advanced Data Assimilation Systems for Operational Monitoring and Forecasting of the North Atlantic and Nordic Seas) we have considered advanced data assimilation techniques which are validated and implemented with the Ocean General Circulation Model MICOM (Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model), a seven compartment ecosystem model based on the Fasham, Ducklow and McKelvie model (FDM) *Fasham et al.* (1990) and a sea-ice model, to build a preoperational marine monitoring and forecasting system.

The major objective of the project has been to implement and demonstrate novel sophisticated data assimilation methods such as the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) *Evensen* (1994), the Ensemble Kalman Smoother (EnKS) *Evensen and van Leeuwen* (2000) and the Singular Evolutive Extended Kalman Filter (SEEK) *Pham et al.* (1998) with realistic ocean models. The use of the advanced data assimilation methods makes it possible to perform a multivariate and physically consistent analysis with statistical covariance functions which vary in time and space. This allows us to extract a maximum amount of information from observations of surface properties. The project has involved partners from six European countries working with ocean and ecosystem modeling, data assimilation and processing of remotely sensed observations.

The implementation of the assimilation system has been completed and the data assimilated into MICOM are remotely sensed SLA and SST data, while ocean color data were used for assimilation in the ecosystem model in April to August 2001. In August the physical and ecosystem models were decoupled and we converted from MICOM to the hybrid model HYCOM (references). This was the first step towards the improved forecasting system that will be developed in the EC-funded TOPAZ project. An extensive validation and evaluation work has been carried out in order to assess the impact of data assimilation for the DIADEM real time system run at NERSC (using the MICOM and the EnKF). This paper presents some of the results from the validation work which basically has consisted in comparing vertical model temperature and salinity profiles with independent data from the GTSP data base.

In section 2 the isopycnal coordinate ocean model, MICOM, is presented, followed by a description of the EnKF data assimilation technique in section 3. Section 4 gives a description of the DIADEM real time monitoring and prediction system. The remotely sensed data and the GTSP data used for validation are presented in section 5 and 6. The numerical results and a concluding remark are given in section 7 and 8, respectively.

2 MICOM

In the DIADEM real time forecasting system we have used the isopycnic dynamic-thermodynamic ocean general circulation model MICOM which is developed by Bleck and coworkers at the university of Miami, *Bleck and Boudra* (1986); *Bleck et al.* (1989, 1992); *Smith et al.* (1990). In this model, the density is used as a vertical coordinate since the density stratification is a monotone function of depth. The motivation behind using an isopycnic ocean model is that mixing occurs mainly along neutral surfaces, i.e. approximately surfaces of constant density. The mixing across the constant density surfaces is orders of magnitude less than along surfaces, and can therefore be neglected in most experiments. Hence in our model the ocean is divided into a number of constant density layers where the density increases with depth. The interaction between the different layers is due to diapycnal mixing and hydrostatic pressure forces, and the isopycnic nature of the model gives a complete control over non-isopycnic mixing processes between the layers. The isopycnic formulation also provides high resolution in large density gradient regions, and artificial mixing only occurs along density surfaces where it is negligible compared to the eddy mixing. The mixed layer, i.e. the upper layer allows for horizontal variations in density and the thermodynamic variables. It is based on the Kraus-Turner (*Bleck et al.*, 1989) and the formulation by (*Gaspar et al.*, 1990).

The model solves a number of equations consisting of the momentum equation for the velocity vector, two conservation equations for salt and heat, a continuity equation for mass conservation and finally the hydrostatic pressure equation which relates pressure to depth. These equations are given and discussed in *Bleck et al.* (1992). MICOM permits motion in all layers (contrary to reduced gravity models which suppress the barotropic waves). In order to reduce the numerical cost of carrying the barotropic waves, a split-explicit scheme is used, see *Higdon and Bennett* (1996). The momentum and continuity equations are solved for the barotropic and baroclinic velocities and pressure fields, respectively. The barotropic equations are integrated forward with small time steps a time interval equal to one baroclinic time step. The baroclinic equations are then stepped forward one time step using the new pressure field.

In MICOM it is assumed that all layers exist everywhere in the model domain and they are allowed to become massless. The thickness of the layers is entirely determined by the model equations and special algorithms maintaining positive definiteness must be used for integrating the continuity equation for layer thicknesses. The layer will outcrop to the bottom of the ocean and to the upper layer. MICOM is coupled

to an ice model and there are thermodynamical variables in all layers.

3 Data Assimilation with the Ensemble Kalman filter

The EnKF was designed to resolve two major problems related to the use of the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) with nonlinear dynamics in large state spaces. The EKF applies a closure scheme where third- and higher order moments in the error covariance equation are discarded. The linearization used in the error covariance equation has been shown to be invalid in a number of applications, e.g., *Evensen (1992)* and *Miller et al. (1994)*. In fact, the equation is no longer the fundamental equation for the error evolution when the dynamical model is nonlinear. In *Evensen (1994)* it was shown that a Monte Carlo method can be used as an alternative to the approximated error covariance equation in the EKF. In EnKF a Monte Carlo method is used to solve an equation for the time evolution of the probability density of the model state. In the following the equation for this probability density function is outlined.

For a nonlinear model where we appreciate that the model is not perfect and contains model errors we can write it as a stochastic differential equation (on continuous form) as

$$d\boldsymbol{\psi} = f(\boldsymbol{\psi})dt + d\mathbf{q}. \quad (1)$$

This equation says that an increment in time will yield an increment in $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ and in addition there is contribution $d\mathbf{q}$ from the model errors. From this equation one can derive the Fokker-Planck or Kolmogorov's equation which describes the time evolution of the probability density $\phi(\boldsymbol{\psi})$ of the model state,

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \sum_i f_i \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \psi_i} = \sum_{i,j} \frac{Q_{ij}}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \psi_i \partial \psi_j} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{Q} = \overline{d\mathbf{q}d\mathbf{q}^T}$ is the covariance matrix for the model errors. This equation does not apply any important approximations and can be considered as the fundamental equation for the time evolution of error statistics. A detailed derivation is given in *Jazwinski (1970)*. The equation describes the change of probability density in a local "volume" which is dependent on the divergence term describing a probability flux into the local "volume" (impact of the dynamical equation) and the diffusion term which tends to flatten the probability density due to the effect of stochastic model errors. If (2) could be solved for the probability density function, it should be possible to calculate statistical moments like the mean state and the error covariance for the model forecast to be used in the analysis scheme.

The EnKF applies a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method to solve (2). The probability density can be represented using a large ensemble of model states and by integrating these model states forward in time according to the model dynamics described by the stochastic differential equation (1), this ensemble prediction is equivalent to solving the Fokker Planck equation using a MCMC method. This procedure forms the backbone for the EnKF. When ever measurements are available a clever analysis procedure is

used to consistently update the ensemble of model states to create a new ensemble with error statistics representing the new analysis.

The forecast model states, $\psi_j, j = 1, \dots, nrens$, are stored in a matrix $A \in R^{m \times nrens}$, where m is the number of variables times the total number of model grid points.

The ensemble approximation of the forecast model covariances is then given by

$$P_e^f = \frac{1}{nrens - 1} (A^f - \bar{A}^f)(A^f - \bar{A}^f)^T, \quad (3)$$

where each column of the matrix $\bar{A}^f$ is the "mean-of-the-ensemble" state, $\bar{\psi} = (1/nrens) \sum_{k=1}^{nrens} \psi_k$. The ensemble mean, $\bar{\psi}$ is considered to be the best guess estimate, and the spreading of the ensemble around the mean represents the error variance in the ensemble. In order to obtain a variance minimizing analysis scheme, we also need to generate an ensemble of observation states, which is done by adding an error term to the observation data

$$d_j = d + \epsilon_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, nrens. \quad (4)$$

ϵ_j is a vector of observation noise, which is picked randomly from a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and standard deviation equal to the measurement standard deviation. The measurement error covariance matrix is then given by

$$W \approx W_e = \overline{\epsilon \epsilon^T}. \quad (5)$$

where the overline denotes an expectation value. Each ensemble member, $\psi_j, j = 1, \dots, nrens$ is updated according to

$$\psi_j^a = \psi_j^f + K_e(d_j - H\psi_j^f), \quad (6)$$

where

$$K_e = P_e^f H^T (H P_e^f H^T + W_e)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

is the Kalman gain matrix which contains information about both model and observation error statistics. The matrix H represents a measurement operator that "measures" the model data at the locations of the observation data.

4 The real time data assimilation system

The real time ocean monitoring and forecasting system with the MICOM and EnKF has been operated since October-November 2000.

Model configuration

An orthogonal curvilinear grid with a pronounced resolution in the Nordic Seas has been used in the DIADEM model system. This model grid includes the North Atlantic and the Arctic. The resolution is

Figure 1: The DIADEM model grid

enhanced in the Nordic Seas while a high resolution is still retained in the Seas off Europe. Thus a proper representation of the inflow of Atlantic water, with its temperature, salinity and content of nutrients, into the Nordic Seas can be maintained. The use of a variable model resolution and a large model domain allow us to apply "closed" boundaries far from the area of interest where a relaxation to climatology is applied.

In the fine resolution areas (Nordic Seas), the grid (with 280 times 260 horizontal grid cells) has a resolution of about 12 km, see Figure 2. Note that only every second grid point is plotted in the figure. The number of vertical layers is 17. The following density values have been considered in the isopycnic layers (from the upper layer to the lower layer): $\sigma_1 = 24.0450$, $\sigma_2 = 24.9551$, $\sigma_3 = 25.6802$, $\sigma_4 = 26.2511$, $\sigma_5 = 26.6919$, $\sigma_6 = 27.0286$, $\sigma_7 = 27.2874$, $\sigma_8 = 27.4947$, $\sigma_9 = 27.6650$, $\sigma_{10} = 27.8010$, $\sigma_{11} = 27.9018$, $\sigma_{12} = 27.9706$, $\sigma_{13} = 28.0214$, $\sigma_{14} = 28.0527$, $\sigma_{15} = 28.0805$, $\sigma_{16} = 28.1019$, $\sigma_{17} = 28.1150$.

Spin up of the physical model system

The model has been spun up in a simulation run throughout year 1999 until September 2000. Next an ensemble of 100 model states has been generated by perturbing the layer interfaces in the spun up model state. The perturbations were drawn from a sample of smooth pseudo-random fields with mean equal to zero and a prescribed covariance. The algorithm described by *Evensen* (1994) was used to generate the fields. *Evensen* (1994) also presented an algorithm for introducing a specified predetermined correlation between a sample of pseudo random fields by choosing each new sample as a specific linear combination of the original fields. Multiplication of each pseudo-random field, having zero mean and variance equal to one, with a constant σ will lead to a new sample with variance equal to σ^2 . The initial ensemble was thus created by adding smooth and vertically correlated pseudo-random fields drawn from a sample with mean equal to zero and for each vertical layer the variance represents 10% of the layer thickness at that location. This results in a sample of model states which all have a slightly different stratification. These differences should be a measure of our confidence in the watermass characteristics of the model initial conditions. From this initial ensemble a short spin-up simulation is required to ensure that the model state for each individual ensemble member is in dynamical balance. The ensemble of model states was therefore integrated throughout September 2000, subject to random atmospheric forcing that represents the dominant source of modelling error.

Random atmospheric forcing

Model errors include both errors of model physics (forcing errors, errors in parameterization, etc) and errors in the numerical solution methods. In the EnKF, EnKS and in the spin-up of the ensemble, it is assumed that the dominant model errors are connected to mis-specifications of atmospheric forcing fields used to compute the surface fluxes. Thus, we have treated the atmospheric forcing as a stochastic process and added spatially and temporally correlated random fields to the atmospheric data. Hence, random atmospheric forcing has been added in order to simulate modeling errors. Pseudo random fields have been calculated from a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and given standard deviation and were added to the atmospheric forcing data. The random fields are independent for each member and the horizontal decorrelation length is 10 km. For the different atmospheric fields we have used the following standard deviations: $\sigma_{\text{airtemperature}} = 3.0^\circ \text{C}$, $\sigma_{\text{windspeed}} = 5.0 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $\sigma_{\text{windstress}} = 0.5 \text{ g cm}^{-1} \text{ s}^2$.

Assimilation cycles

The assimilation cycle for the physical ocean model, which started in October 2000, is explained in the following. Every Thursday (day J+8) SLA, SST and ECMWF data sets are downloaded from public ftp sites. The remotely sensed data correspond to the state on Wednesday the week before, i.e. day J. The ensemble of forecast model states has been integrated up to day J and the remote sensing data are assimilated

using the EnKF method. Next, the analysed ensemble of model states is integrated one week, until day J+7 using the ECMWF analysis data for atmospheric forcing. Finally, the mean state of the forecast ensemble is forecasted another week, until day J+14, using the forecast EMCWF data. The forecast state on this day is put on the public DIADEM webpage.

From April throughout August 2001 the MICOM run in coupled mode with the FDM ecosystem model. Note that the physical and biochemical data assimilation systems were decoupled. That is, SLA and SST data are only used to update the physical variables, and the (evolving) physical sub-state is then used to force the biochemical model. Similarly, the assimilation of SeaWiFS chlorophyll data provides an updated biochemical sub-state.

Real time forecasts displayed on internet

Examples of forecast of MICOM variable can be found in Figure 2. The plots have been downloaded from the DIADEM real time webpage, which has been generated by the Halo Laboratory of Oceanic and Atmospheric Sciences (HALO) and is located at www.halo.is/diadem/rtweb. Figure 2 shows forecasts of SST and Sea Surface Salinity (SSS) on June 6th 2001. The data have been produced at NERSC using the MICOM and the EnKF. Several other variables are currently available on the forecast site: forecast of Sea Surface Height (SSH), Sea Surface Anomalies (SLA), mixed layer thickness, surface current in addition the remote sensing data that are assimilated, i.e. SST, SLA and Chlorophyll-a from Joint Research Centre (JRC), Italy. From April throughout August forecast of variables from the FDM ecosystem modelrun were also available, i.e. phytoplankton, nitrate and dissolved inorganic carbon.

5 The observation data

The Sea Level Anomalies data

The Collecte Localisation Satellites (CLS) has produced the combined TopexPoseidon and ERS-2 altimeter data for the real-time exercise. The altimeter data acquisition and processing system has been operated routinely and maintained since November 2000. The altimeter products, which have a $1/4^\circ$ resolution, have been provided to the modelling groups every Thursday.

The Reynolds SST data products from CDC

Reynolds SST data provided by the *NOAA-CIRES Climate Diagnostics Center*, Boulder, Colorado, USA, is assimilated into the DIADEM realtime ocean monitoring and forecasting system. The data is available from the Web site at <http://www.cdc.noaa.gov/>. The optimum interpolation (OI) SST analysis is produced weekly on a 1° grid. The analysis uses *in situ* and satellite SST's simulated by sea-ice cover. Before the analysis is computed, the satellite data is adjusted for biases using the method of *Reynolds (1998)* and *Reynolds and Marsico (1993)*. A description of the OI analysis can be found in *Reynolds and Smith (1994)*.

GTSP profiles and products

A cooperative international project, the GTSP seeks to develop and maintain a global ocean temperature and salinity resource with data that are both up-to-date and of the highest quality possible. Both real-time data transmitted over the Global Telecommunications System (GTS), and delayed-mode data received by the National Oceanographic Data Center (NODC) are acquired and incorporated into a continuously managed database.

In the DIADEM project, temperature and salinity profiles extracted from the GTSP data base have been used to validate the real time ocean forecasts of physical variables and to assess the impact of assimilating SST and SLA data.

6 Results

An extensive validation and evaluation work has been carried out in order to assess the impact of data assimilation for the real time system run at NERSC (using the MICOM and the EnKF). In the following some of the results of this validation work are presented.

Validation with GTSP data

Temperature and salinity profiles measured on April 25th 2001 have been extracted from the GTSP data base. Only data profiles with maximum depth exceeding 500 meters within the region 10S to 70N and 80W to 10E have been selected in order to limit the total number of profiles. Only one salinity profile was available while the number of temperature profiles selected were 16. The locations of the GTSP data profiles are given in Figure 3.

The corresponding profiles from a free run simulation (i.e. with no data assimilation) and the real time assimilation run have been calculated. The startdate of the freerun simulation has been February 26th 2001. The model profiles that resulted from the assimilation run were calculated using the mean field of the analysed ensemble files on April 24th as initial data. In the sampling of the model data we have used bilinear interpolation in the horizontal and a spline interpolation in the vertical in order to match the longitude, latitude and depth locations of the observation data.

Some of the model profiles and observed profiles for April 25th are intercompared in Figure 4, 5 and 6. The plots show temperature in degree Celsius or salinity in g/kg along the horizontal axes, and the depth along the vertical axes. In general the assimilation run profiles are the closest to the observation profiles, and especially the effect of the data assimilation is positive in the surface water and for the salinity profile (profile 6). However, for profiles 9, 10 and 13 the freerun SST is somewhat better than the SST from the assimilation run (compared to the observed SST). These profiles are all located in the turbulent, highly energetic central Gulf Stream region where the model, which suffers from a rather coarse resolution,

exhibits problems with reproducing fronts and eddies in the ocean.

We have calculated Root Mean Square error (RMS) values for the temperature profiles, both for the total depth of the profile and for data collected in specific depth intervals of the profiles; 0-200 meters, 200-400 meters, 400-600 meters, 600-800 meters and finally 800-1000 meters. The results of the RMS calculation for each profile can be found in Figure 7. The profile number is given on the horizontal axes and the RMS values on the vertical axes. In general the assimilation run results in lower RMS values than the free run, especially in the upper 400 meters of the ocean. However, this tendency typically decreases as a function of depth, indicating that the assimilation impacts the model most in the upper part of the ocean. For some of the profiles in the Gulf Stream region (e.g. 11 and 12), the free run RMS values are lower than the assimilation run RMS values at deep water, see RMS values calculated at 600-800 meters and 800-1000 meters depth. Consequently, the RMS values for the entire profiles are lower for the free run than the assimilation run data. Also, the results indicate that the central Gulf Stream region is a turbulent area where the model, which suffers from a coarse resolution, fails to reproduce fronts and rings in the ocean even when the model is forced with data assimilation. However, in general the data assimilation seems to have a positive impact, at least for the upper 500-600 meters of the ocean.

Model and observation misfits

The remote sensing and model data have also been intercompared in order to assess the impact of assimilating SLA and SST data. The impact has been examined by comparing the observed data with the corresponding forecast, analysis and free run data from the model. Figure 8 upper-left shows the observed SST on April 25th, and the upper-right and lower-left plots show the difference (in absolute value) between the observed and forecast SST and observed and analysis SST, respectively. The discrepancies between the model and observation data have clearly decreased when assimilating SLA and SST. Moreover, the discrepancy between the observed and forecast SST is smaller than the difference between observed and free run SST, compare upper-right and lower-right plots. This again illustrates that the EnKF data assimilation efficiently forces the model SST towards the observed state and keep it close to the satellite data. We have also calculated weekly RMS values of SLA and SST misfits between the model and observation data for the free run, the assimilation run and the 14 days forecast, which results from 14 days forecasting after last analysis. The RMS calculation starts on April 25th, which corresponds to Juliantday 18742. The results, which are shown in Figure 9, again illustrate how assimilation of SLA and SST data forces the model towards the observed data. The difference in RMS values for the forecast data corresponding to the assimilation run and the 14 days forecasting, can mainly be explained by the fact that *forecast* ECMWF data have been used the last week of the 14 days forecasting simulation while only ECMWF *analysis* data have been used in the assimilation run.

SLA and SST model biases

Finally we show plots of the time-mean of the misfit-sequence for the SST and SLA data, both for the freerun simulation and the assimilation (real time) run. Figure 10 shows mean fields for the free run simulation (upper) and the assimilation run (lower). The mean fields corresponding to the assimilation run are closer to zero than the mean fields corresponding to the free run simulation. This shows that the EnKF assimilation forces the model state towards the observed state and reduces the SLA and SST biases in the model simulation.

Time-depth plots

The EnKF is a multivariate analysis schemes, meaning that all the variables in the model are updated according to the covariances that exist between the model variables and the observation data. These covariances are approximated using the ensemble of forecasted model states. Figure 11 shows the impact of assimilating SLA and SST on the model temperature, zonal and meridional velocity at 39.2°W and 43.3°N . The plots show the time evolution of these variables (from day 144 to day 177 year 2001) at this specific location for both the assimilation run (left) and the corresponding free-run simulation (right). The negative depth layer in the two uppermost plots represent the observed SST and the vertical black lines indicate the data assimilation point of time. Clearly, the model temperature and velocity components are updated in the EnKF analysis step and the updates in temperature (at least in the mixed layer) are consistent with the observed SST. Moreover, the mixed layer thickness is decreased when model SST is increased and vice versa. This is consistent with the negative correlations that exist between SST and mixed layer thickness.

The time evolution of the variables from the free-run simulation is smoother than the corresponding evolution in the assimilation run. Moreover, the EnKF assimilation also seems to have a strong influence on the general ocean circulation in the long run, since the free-run and assimilation plots in Figure 11 give rather different pictures of the ocean state at the specific location.

Time evolution of modelling errors

The errors in the model are approximated from the ensemble of model states. A large spreading in the ensemble give a large variance estimate for the variables and hence large modelling errors. The time evolution of some of the model variables is given in Figure 12 and 13. The variances are plotted for two days, i.e. day 291 year 2000 (left) and day 184 year 2001 (right). Clearly, the variances have decreased almost everywhere in the model domain during the assimilation run. This is caused by the EnKF assimilation of SLA and SST, that efficiently reduces the model errors (variances) in the analysis steps. Note that the reduction in variances for the different variables reflects the multivariate nature of the EnKF analysis scheme.

7 Concluding remark

We have considered a validation of the DIADEM real time ocean monitoring and forecasting system with the MICOM and the EnKF. Temperature and salinity profiles from the GTSP data base have been compared with the corresponding model data from the assimilation and free run simulations on day April 25th 2001. In addition we have intercompared the satellite data and the corresponding model data in order to assess the impact of assimilating SLA and SST data.

The intercomparison of satellite and model data with calculation of error RMS values shows that the EnKF assimilation of SLA and SST efficiently forces the model state towards the observed state. Moreover, in general, the intercomparison of vertical temperature and salinity profiles and calculation of corresponding RMS values indicate that the ocean circulation is improved when assimilating SLA and SST data. However, the results show that especially the central Gulf Stream region is a rather turbulent region, where the model exhibits problems with reproducing fronts and eddies in the ocean. We therefore believe that a higher resolution in this area and assimilation of additional *in situ* data, e.g. temperature, salinity and current profiles, is necessary in order to optimize the positive impact of the EnKF assimilation on the general ocean circulation.

The DIADEM system will be subject to further improvements and extensions in the TOPAZ project (kickoff in January 2001). In TOPAZ the MICOM has been substituted with the HYCOM (providing finer vertical resolution in the mixed layer), and in addition the assimilation tools will be prepared for assimilation of new or upcoming observation data. Examples of such are SSS from the SMOS satellite, ice concentration and ice thickness (from Cryosat), and *in situ* vertical temperature and salinity profiles from bouys. We believe that the future DIADEM/TOPAZ system will provide valuable oceanic information, both in hindcast and forecast mode and on regional and global scale.

Figure 2:

Figure 3: The localization of the GTSP data profiles on April 25th 2001.

Figure 4: Intercomparison of GTSP and model produced data profiles.

Figure 5: Intercomparison of GTSP and model produced data profiles.

Figure 6: Intercomparison of GTSP and model produced data profiles.

Figure 7: RMS-calculation of the model misfit to the GTSP data.

Figure 8: Observed SST data on April 25th and the differences between the observation data and model data (forecast (upper-right), analysis (lower-left) and free-run data (lower-right)).

Figure 9: RMS-calculation of model misfits to the observed SLA (upper) and SST (lower) data.

Figure 10: Plots of the time-mean of the misfits sequence for the SLA (left) and SST (right) data. Model data from the free-run run (upper) and assimilation run (lower).

Figure 11: Time-depth plots of temperature and velocity components at location 39.2°W and 43.3°N. Free run data (right) and assimilation run data (left).

Figure 12: Variances in SST, SSH and mixed layer thickness (DP(1)).

Figure 13: Variances in barotropic pressure (PB), barotropic velocity (u-component) (UB) and mixed layer density (TH).

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